

MUSIC TEACHERS NATIONAL ASSOCIATION

The Carew Tower • 441 Vine Street, Suite 505 • Cincinnati, Ohio 45202-2814 • Phone: (513) 421-1420 • Fax: (513) 421-2503

MTNA Convention Features Collaborative Artistry

Dear Colleague,

Each year Music Teachers National Association presents a national convention unparalleled in quality and value for collegiate and independent music teachers of all disciplines. I'm especially excited about this year's event, and enthusiastically invite you to participate.

The 1998 convention will include a special focus on the ensemble arts, providing an opportunity for us to meet, share and learn. Of particular interest is a concert scheduled for March 30, "Celebration of the Collaborative Arts," featuring well-known artists playing music for various combinations of piano, voice, strings and woodwinds.

Other special convention sessions will include a presentation by high school chamber music groups from Baton Rouge, Louisiana, and an evening gathering for networking and planning future conferences. I'd be happy to send you more detailed information about all that's planned for the convention—just fill out the enclosed form and fax it to my attention at MTNA national headquarters at (513) 421-2503. Or send an e-mail message to jwwhaley@mtna.org.

This year's convention is just the beginning! If you have specific topics to suggest for future conventions, please include your ideas on the fax-back form. Also, because we want to include all musicians interested in the ensemble arts, I invite you to send us the names and addresses of your instrumental and vocal colleagues who might appreciate receiving information about the convention.

I hope you will participate in this unique new opportunity for collaborative musicians. Won't you please join me at the 1998 MTNA National Convention in Nashville, March 28–April 1? I look forward to welcoming you.

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Jean Barr". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Jean Barr

Professor, and Director of the Program in Piano Accompanying and Chamber Music, Eastman School of Music

**Music Teachers National Association
Fax-back Quick Reply Form**

Please complete and fax this form to Jean Barr at (513) 421-2503.

MTNA is pleased to announce a special focus on the ensemble arts at the 1998 National Convention, and invites all collaborative artists to participate in this premiere event in Nashville, Tennessee on March 28–April 1. Respond right away to take advantage of an early registration discount.

- I am interested in attending. Please send convention information.
- Please send MTNA membership information. (You may be eligible for 6-month membership, a great way to give MTNA a “test run” and enjoy full benefits, including the member rate for convention.)

Your name, title, address, phone, fax, e-mail: _____

What topics would interest you in future sessions devoted to ensemble arts?

In addition to convention sessions, would you be interested in participating in future breakfast/lunch “round table” discussions? yes no

If you have colleagues who would be interested, please list their names, positions, addresses, phones, faxes, e-mails: _____

Memo: Rex Whiddon
Joan Reist
Gary Ingle

From: Collaborative Arts Steering Committee

As we participate in this year's MTNA convention, we are renewed in our commitment to contribute all that we can to enrich the activities of this important organization. We are looking forward to the future and are confident that the strong leadership of our colleague, Jean Barr will continue. In her capacity as program chair of collaborative performance she provides a beacon and focus for our mutual interest. Her ongoing presence in this role ensures our future success.

May we take this opportunity to thank you for recognizing the value of collaborative arts in the education of young musicians. We appreciate particularly the initial support and encouragement of Margaret Lorince and hope to reinforce our presence in the pedagogical arena.

Signed,

Anne Epperson (Cleveland Institute) on behalf of:
James Howsmon (Oberlin)
Lynn Jemison-Keisker (Louisiana State University)
Marilyn Neeley (The Catholic University of America)
Eckart Sellheim (Arizona State)
Robert Spillman (University of Colorado)
Sylvia Wang (Northwestern University)

MUSIC TEACHERS NATIONAL ASSOCIATION

The Carew Tower • 441 Vine Street, Suite 505 • Cincinnati, Ohio 45202-2814 • Phone: (513) 421-1420 • Fax: (513) 421-2503

April 15, 1999

Jean Barr
19 Evergreen Lane
Rochester, NY 14618

Dear Jean:

On behalf of the Board of Directors, we write to express our deepest appreciation to you for the exceptional work you have accomplished during the 1997-1999 biennium as Chair of the Collaborative Arts Committee. Your willingness to give unselfishly of your expertise and time to advance the work of our association is commendable. The accomplishments realized under your leadership will positively impact our association for many years to come.

It is gratifying to know that the important work of the Collaborative Arts Committee will remain in your competent hands during the coming biennium. Again, thank you for all that you have done, and will continue to do, for MTNA.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "L. Rexford Whiddon".

L. Rexford Whiddon
President

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Gary L. Ingle".

Gary L. Ingle
Executive Director

MUSIC TEACHERS NATIONAL ASSOCIATION

L. Rexford Whiddon, NCTM
President

August 6, 1998

Dr. Jean M. Barr
19 Evergreen Lane
Rochester, NY 14618

Dear Jean:

I am delighted to inform you that the MTNA Board of Directors, at their July meeting, enthusiastically approved the establishment of a MTNA Collaborative Performance Advisory Committee. On behalf of the Board, it is my pleasure to confirm your appointment as the first Chair of the committee. Your term as chair begins immediately and will conclude following the 2001 MTNA convention in Washington, D.C.

The following purpose was approved to guide the work of the committee:

1. To advance the study and performance of chamber music.
2. To provide opportunities for communication and collaboration among those interested in the teaching and performing of chamber music.
3. To recommend major collaborative arts initiatives, projects and services to the MTNA Board of Directors.

The Board also approved the following for membership on this committee:

Sylvia Beaudette
Paula Fan
Lynn Jemison-Keisker
Eckart Sellheim
Robert Spillman
Sylvia Wang

Anne Epperson
James Howsmon
Marilyn Neeley
Judy Kehler Siebert
Carolyn True

Official letters of appointment will be sent to the above individuals within the next few days.

Jean, I am delighted that the MTNA Board of Directors has approved this important new initiative for our association! I am confident that under your superb leadership, and with the support of your distinguished colleagues, the collaborative arts will flourish as never before within our association.

Dr. Jean M. Barr
Page 2

I can think of no other movement with more potential for fostering a *sense of community* within MTNA. I look forward to continuing to work with you in the months ahead.

In addition to postage and telephone expenses related to your position, MTNA will provide round trip travel to the 1999, 2000 and 2001 conventions and 2 nights lodging at one-half the double occupancy rate.

I will appreciate receiving confirmation by letter of your acceptance of this appointment at your earliest convenience. In the meantime, my best wishes to you for much success during the coming academic year.

Cordially,

L. Rexford Whiddon, NCTM
President

LRW/ds

cc: Joan Reist, MTNA President-Elect
Gary Ingle, MTNA Executive Director
Wayne Gibson, MTNA Treasurer

enclosure: Expense Form

Jean M. Barr

19 Evergreen Lane, Rochester, NY 14618
Tel (716) 271-8156 Fax (716) 271-1716

E-mail: jbarr@uhura.cc.rochester.edu or JeanMBarr@aol.com

November 5, 1998

L. Rexford Whiddon, President
Music Teachers National Association
The Carew Tower
441 Vine Street, Suite 505
Cincinnati, OH 45202-2814
Fax: (513) 421-2503

Dear Rex,

I am absolutely delighted that the MTNA Board of Directors has approved the establishment of a Collaborative Performance Advisory Committee. As you know, this has been a long-held dream of mine and I am gratified to see it come to fruition. It will be my honor and privilege to serve as the committee's first chair. Thank you for your continued enthusiastic support.

Cordially,

Jean Barr

On behalf of the newly-established Collaborative Performance Advisory Committee, I would like to extend our thanks to the MTNA Board of Directors for appreciating the importance of the collaborative arts and integrating them into MTNA in a formal way. As the Board is aware, until now there has been no national forum for musicians interested in collaborative performance to meet and exchange ideas.

My colleagues and I have met informally to discuss how we might best contribute to MTNA and to the profession at large. Among the interesting proposals emerging from that meeting are the following:

- 1.) Annually, we will provide the MTNA National Competitions Chair with a list of well-qualified accompanists (living in that year's convention city) who may be contacted to partner the competitors.
- 2.) With the growing interest in chamber music nationally, we would like to pursue the following:
 - a.) Seek to encourage MTNA, ASTA, MENC, NATS, the Flute Society, etc. to declare a "Year of Chamber Music." In that year, each organization could:
 - commission intermediate level chamber music compositions,
 - designate that any student composition competitions focus on chamber music for intermediate level performers, and
 - jointly persuade publishers to publish the best of those compositions.
 - b.) Compile a list of Intermediate Level Chamber Music, published by MTNA and made available for purchase nationwide – not just to MTNA members.
- 3.) Compile a list of summer activities for collaborative musicians of all ages
- 4.) Compile a list of Collaborative Repertoire for the Young Student
- 5.) Compile a list of Suggested Vocal Repertoire for the High School Student
- 6.) Compile a Directory of College and University Accompanying Programs.
- 7.) Create a number of pamphlets, to be published by MTNA, such as:
 - a.) "How to identify and prepare a promising student for a career in the collaborative arts"
 - b.) "Tips for including ensemble experiences in your studio teaching"
- 8.) Because collaborative performers have had no formal affiliation, other than with Chamber Music America, musicians in this specialized field have had no forum in which to exchange ideas (e.g. how to create courses or programs in chamber music and accompanying.) We would like to have 1 or 2 sessions at each convention designed specifically to address such topics.

The committee eagerly looks forward to pursuing these ideas and others, and we greatly appreciate the opportunity to be a part of MTNA.

- 1.) Work with MTNA, ASTA, MENC, NATS, the Flute Society, etc. to declare a "Year of Chamber Music." In that year, hopefully the year 2000 or 2001, each organization would agree to:
 - a.) commission intermediate level chamber music compositions,
 - b.) designate that any student composition competitions focus on chamber music for intermediate level performers, and
 - c.) jointly persuade publishers to publish the best of those compositions.
- 2.) Compile a list of Intermediate Level Chamber Music, ultimately to be published by MTNA and made available for purchase nationwide – not just to MTNA members.
- 3.) Compile a list of summer activities for collaborative musicians of all ages

There would appear to be a growing national interest in offering music students of all levels the opportunity of playing chamber music. The chamber music experience can enhance the ability to listen and to communicate - verbally and musically. Many younger musicians find it to be a social activity as well. While there is an abundance of repertoire for the advanced musician, there is relatively little for the intermediate level performer. To foster that culture, the Collaborative Performance Advisory Committee would like to begin a series of projects, the first of which are proposed above.